

Cevik's three-cycle acupuncture (CTCA)

Cemal Cevik *

Department of Traditional and Complementary Medicine, Medical Faculty, Lokman Hekim University, Turkey.

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Abstract

Three-cycle acupuncture is a new acupuncture practice. This application is an objective patient-oriented application instead of subjective methods used in diagnosing acupuncture. Thus, the diagnosis and treatment of acupuncture are enlightened and made easier. The proper flow and quality of Chi are fundamental to treatment and optimal health in Chinese medicine. In the body, the channels of energy known as meridians connect to the internal organs so that the qi of the organs flows to its associated body parts. In Chinese Traditional Medicine, energy flows through our 12 main meridians or energetic pathways, in two-hour blocks. Chi begins its daily flow in the Lungs and traverses to the Large Intestine before continuing to its next destination. It finally stops at the Liver, before it begins again. If the chi is blocked in a certain organ, it will not be able to completely activate that organ or continue its journey with enough intensity to fully benefit the next organ system. If we provide the flow of Chi in the pathological cycle, the cycle starts and the complaints disappear. With this acceptance, we introduced the concept of three-cycle acupuncture. Thus, we can only perform treatment without the need for another diagnosis method. We used the Yuan points of the organs belonging to the pathological cycle to remove the obstruction. The method was very effective and we got very good answers. We have been using the method in our polyclinics for five years.

Keywords: Chi flow; Channel; Acupuncture; Three cycle treatment

1. Introduction

Acupuncture diagnosis in its current form is a subjective treatment that requires a lot of experience and often changes according to doctors. Although it is a very effective treatment method, the difference in applications creates difficulties in the widespread use of acupuncture. In this new method, which we call three-loop acupuncture, the differences between physicians were tried to be eliminated, and a faster and more effective response was tried to be obtained with less needling (four needles). The Daoist philosophical approach is a close relationship between humankind and nature. Concepts of qi can be noted by Daoist writers such as Lao Zi, Zhuang Zi, and Lao-Zhuang. Chi was used to explaining the workings of the entire universe. As a microcosm of the universe, the concept of qi made its way into medical writings. Chi became known as the vital substance of living beings. Medical theorists postulated that just as qi was seen to drive wind through the sky, collect in mountains, and course from the river to the sea, qi must certainly follow these same principles within the body. This becomes the basis of anatomy and physiology in Chinese medicine. It is known to practitioners of acupuncture Chinese medicine as the Jing Luo (1). The *Huangdi Neijing* ("The Yellow Emperor's Classic of Medicine", circa 2nd century BCE) is historically credited with first establishing the pathways, called meridians, through which qi allegedly circulates in the human body (2,3). In traditional Chinese medicine, symptoms of various illnesses are believed to be either the product of disrupted, blocked, and unbalanced qi movement through meridians or deficiencies and imbalances of qi in the *Zang-Fu* organs (4) when speaking of Chi in the context of TCM, it is treated as the moving force behind the functions of the organs ("Kidney Chi", Liver Chi, etc.) and at the same time is considered

* Corresponding author: Cemal Cevik MD

Prof of Clinical Chemistry. Turkey Lokman Hekim University, Medical faculty, Head of Traditional and Complementary Medicine section.

the source that nourishes and sustains all the bodily tissues. The free and unobstructed flow of Chi in the human body is at the root of health. According to TCM, the natural state of humans is a healthy one. If there is a proper circulation of Chi in the body, this state of health continues, but if the flow is obstructed, conditions are created that can lead to the onset of more or less serious pathologies. Just as an example, a bruise is considered a blockage of Blood and Chi in TCM, while a cold is caused by an invasion of external pathogens that have managed to circumvent the layer of Defensive Chi (Wei Chi) that protects the body (the comparison of Wei Chi to the immune system is evident). According to the millenarian philosophical concepts at the root of TCM, everything that exists is made of Chi. In its more “condensed” forms, Qi becomes matter; the more concentrated it is, the more solid the matter. For example, a rock is a very “condensed” form of Qi, while dirt is a less concentrated form. Liquids are an even less “condensed” form and gases are less concentrated still. Energetic phenomena (such as electromagnetic energy) are very rarefied forms of Chi, while “Shen” (“spirit”) and thought are even more rarefied forms(5). To diagnose diseases, we can take action from symptoms and signs in acupuncture as well as in western medicine. Therefore, it would be appropriate to explain some of the terms we use in diagnosis. Symptom, is an expression that occurs spontaneously, can be seen, heard, and smelled, indicating the discomfort of the person. Skin rash, cough, sputum, discharge, facial flushing, hoarseness, etc. Many examples such as can be given. Most of the time, they constitute the patient's complaints. The finding is that physicians found by examining and requesting some tests. Syndrome, all signs and symptoms that determine a particular disorder, that occur together and facilitate diagnosis are called a syndrome. Syndrome = Symptoms + Signs.

Syndrome is the name given to a special disorder caused by the combination of more than one sign and symptom. All of the signs and symptoms manifest themselves as a specific disorder. the disorder is a lack of order, balance, harmony. Dysharmonia is an imbalance caused by external and internal causes. Here, the imbalance can be expressed as disharmony and dissonance. Dysharmonia can occur both in the body and in the mind. Dysharmonia manifests itself in syndromes. There is dysharmonic in every syndrome.

Identifying syndromes means identifying the underlying incompatibility of all clinical symptoms. Signs and symptoms occur by two factors: Being harmed by a harmful agent (effect) and the body's response (reaction) to this damage. Let's take a look at a syndrome known as a cold wind in acupuncture according to the explanations. Cold type external syndrome (cold-wind), Cold or Wind-Cold syndrome symptoms; Light fever, sometimes no fever, dislike the cold, severe body aches, shake, absence of sweating, absence of thirst, advanced neck stiffness, thin-white tongue, superficial, tight, overflowing pulse.

Figure 1 Wind- Cold Syndrom

Balance disruption and correction, If we give an example, with eating, blood sugar (glucose) rises, imbalance occurs. Symptoms such as dry mouth, desire to drink water, itching may appear. This imbalance occurred with the rise of glucose. If this increase is confirmed by measuring in the laboratory, there will be a finding. This height is detected by the beta cells of the pancreas with the glucokinase enzyme sensor. After perception beta cells begin to secrete insulin (Control enter). Insulin increases glucose entry into muscle tissue (effector organ) and blood glucose level decreases to normal. The organism can repair itself.

1.1. Etiology-Pathogenesis

Etiology is about why the disease develops (cause) and pathogenesis is related to how it develops. The pathogenesis of a disease is the biological (and pathological) changes that occur as the disease develops. Since the two terms are used very intertwined with each other, their usage in an etiopathogenetic way is common. An example of the term etiopathogenesis is the etiology of acute appendicitis; It is fecalitis (petrified stool) or lymphoid hyperplasia obstructing the lumen of the appendix. The pathogenesis of acute appendicitis is the obstruction of the appendix lumen and the accumulation of mucus in the lumen and the growth of bacteria in the closed environment, resulting in swelling of the

appendix, gangrene, and perforation (perforation) as a result of deterioration of the appendix blood circulation due to tension.

2. Etiopathogenesis in acupuncture

Chi channels, which are very thin (primordial system), can cause vasoconstriction in primordial system endothelial cells due to a pathogenic factor such as cold, thus blocking the flow of chee and thus fluid flow and blood flow in that area. This results in obstruction. Factors that cause deterioration of chee flow are pathogenic factors. They are the factors that cause the chee flow to deteriorate. Syndromes occur because of these factors. These factors are divided into two as external and internal factors. External Factors are hot, cold, wind, moisture, dryness. Internal factors are excessive joy, anger, sadness, grief, fear.

2.1. Effects of pathogenic factors (PF)

PFs have two effects; They disrupt normal physiology, making them abnormal (frequent urges), or reveal pathological studies that are not in the normal physiology of organs (coughing). Syndromes occur in these two cases.

2.2. The occurrence of syndromes

With the occurrence of physiological changes (urination, stool, sweating, thirst, sleep),

Pathological changes (coughing, chest tightness, headache, inability to breathe, palpitations), nasal congestion, discharge, itching, etc.

Emotional changes (sadness, joy, crying,)

Perception changes, forgetting, learning disability, memory impairment

2.2.1. Physiological symptoms

Urinating (its frequency, whether it wakes up and urinates at night, whether it is incontinent, whether it is nocturnal, urine color, darkness, odor, etc.). Stool (diarrhea or constipation, hard or soft stool, frequency, odor, etc.). Sweating (without exertion, day or night, localization, etc.). Thirst - (whether with the desire to drink water or not,

2.2.2. Emotional Symptoms

Don't be constantly sad, thoughtful, don't be worried all the time, cry easily, Quick irritation, don't laugh too much, don't be afraid of ordinary things.

2.2.3. Mental conditions

Inability to make easy decisions, inability to concentrate, making the wrong decisions, Inability to form thoughts, being overly afraid or not afraid.

2.3. Syndrome disease difference

There is no single factor determined in the syndrome. The factor is determined in diseases. This is especially the case with bacterial viral diseases. If we give an example from today, the cause of the current pandemic is Coronavirus. The disease agent is the SAR-CoV-2 virus. So this is a viral disease.

Signs (symptoms) and findings that occur and appear together with diseases are gathered under a group. And they are with diseases.

2.4. Diseases and syndrome

In Covid-19 disease, antiphospholipid syndrome, arterial or venous thrombosis, thrombocytopenia, and the presence of antibodies against phospholipid-binding proteins appear.

This syndrome can cause significant morbidity and mortality. Here, the syndrome is like the picture that occurs during the disease. Disease and syndrome can coexist.

2.5. Syndromes in acupuncture

There are approximately 75 syndromes.

There is a Yin Yang imbalance in all syndromes.

The Yin-Yang imbalance is basically due to the insufficient proper flow of the dew flow.

Chee flows to organs through 12 channels for 24 hours. It enters the organs every two hours.

2.6. Classification including most of diseases

- Inflammatory Diseases (Including Infections) -YANG TYPE
- Degenerative Diseases (Excluding Aging) YIN TYPE
- Neoplastic (Tumoral) Diseases-YIN TYPE

2.7. Telocytes and Primovascular system (8, 9)

Chi circulates throughout our body through special channels. The existence of canals (Meridians) through which the dew flows were previously believed only. Dr. from North Korea The existence of channels was demonstrated with the painting technique that Chi Bonghan discovered at the end of the studies he started in 1965, it ceased to be just a belief, it became a scientific entity. Today, the delayed re-dyeing method has been repeated and verified by modern methods. This system, formerly called Bonghan channels, is now called the Primovascular system(8).

This system is the earliest circulatory system in our body. There are four circulatory-communication systems in our body, namely the nervous system, vascular system, lymphatic system, and primo vascular system.

The heart is the governing organ of the blood circulation system, while the lungs are the ruler of the primo vascular system. The lungs send Chi to the whole body.

Telocytes (TCs) are very long, non-neuronal, somatic cells whose function is widely believed to be involved in providing connections between different cells within the body. The cellular characteristics of TCs in various organs have been studied by immunohistochemistry, double immunofluorescence, and electron microscopy in different vertebrate species, and here we investigate the proposed properties of these cells in the context of the “meridian” in Chinese Traditional Medicine (CTM). The results show that TCs and their long extensions, telopodes (Tps) develop a complicated network by homo- and heterocellular junctions in the connective tissue throughout the body, which can connect the skin with distant organs. In concept, this is the analog of ancient meridian maps connecting skin acupoints with the viscera. Various active cells and extracellular vesicles including exosomes move along Tps, which, along with developed mitochondria within the rooms of Tps, may account for the structural evidence for “Chi” (vital energy and signal communication) in CTM. Morphological associations of TCs with the nerve, vascular, endocrine, and immune systems are also compatible with previously proposed meridian theories in CTM. Close relationships exist between TCs and collagen fiber bundles and some structures in skin fascia provide the microanatomical support for acupuncture treatment based on the meridian principle(9)

2.8. Zang and Fu organs

Zang organs are organs that are filled inside. They do more of the storage tasks. The heart, lungs, liver, pericardium, and kidneys are Zang organs. Fu organs are hollow organs. They are more oriented towards creating functions. Gall bladder, bladder, small intestines, and Sanjiao are such organs. Chronic diseases involve the Zang organs. This approach puts Zang's organs in the foreground, bringing them forward. While Fu organs are mostly affected by acute diseases, chronic diseases involve Zang organs. Chronic diseases are difficult to solve and long to treat. Acupuncture patients mostly have chronic diseases. These diseases are treated like Zang diseases. So relieving chronic diseases means keeping chee flowing in Zang organs. Zang organs, disorders in the organ itself and its channels are eliminated by providing flow(4).

These changes turn the physiological events into pathological. These changes cause changes in the mass (YIN) and function (YANG) of the organs.

There may be shrinkage or swelling (enlargement) with inflammation in the masses of the organs. Pathological changes may occur due to pathogenic factors such as cold, heat, humidity, wind, and dryness.

These factors prevent the chi, blood, and body fluids that feed the organs from going to the organs sufficiently. As a result of this obstruction, the organs disrupt the balance between the Yin and Yang within themselves as well as the balance between the conjugated Yang organs. The flow of these basic fuels must be provided and regulated to allow the sick organs the opportunity to repair themselves.

2.9. Removal of Imbalance (Treatment) with three cycles of acupuncture

Twelve basic organs have 12 channels. Energy flow in these bloodlines begins in the lungs and ends in the liver. Twelve organs are divided into three cycles of four each. Within these three cycles, which we call three cycles, there is a sequence of energy flow. When this sequence is broken, pathologies occur. Cycle return is provided by starting from the pathological cycle in treatment. In three cycles, the diagnosis is made by questioning. In the questioning, the patient's personal history, family history, lifestyle, sleep state, calmness or nervousness, whether he has diabetes, or whether he has blood pressure are not asked. The response of the patient is expected without conditioning or directing the patient.

2.10. Diagnosis in three cycles with four organs

The main basis in the three-cycle application is the patient's complaints. The patient is contacted with questions such as "What is that brought you here?" The most important complaint is investigated. The patient may have many complaints, but the most disturbing complaint is asked.

The most important, first complaint is that the organ most affected by the deterioration of chee flow expresses itself to us from the patient's mouth. For example, the main complaint of a 50-year-old female patient is cough. Let the cough be the most important pathological condition of this patient that bothers him. The patient has been coughing for years. This cough makes his life unbearable; that is, the patient has a chronic cough. A chronic cough complaint is a way the lungs expose their troubles. With this complaint, the presence of an irregularity related to the lungs is understood. The lungs normally expand downward and sideways. If their downward movement is impaired, they want to move upward, resulting in a cough. Lungs feed on two different chi. One is the pectoral chi, which is formed by the combination of chee from the air that the lungs take from the air and chee from food coming from the spleen. This union is thought to be around the Ren-17 in the chest. The Ren-17 is known as the sea of chee. Pectoral chee provides the energy necessary for the functioning of the organs in the chest.

However, this energy is energy without knowledge. The fact that it is an information-carrying chee is the result of merging with Yuan chee from the kidney. The pectoral chi is combined with the kidney chee to form the "Right chee". The right chee is the main chee that works the lungs and heart. If the main chee does not reach the lungs sufficiently, the lungs cannot expand downward and sideways and move upward and to the middle in an opposite motion. Cough occurs as a result of this action.

Cough informs that chee flow is blocked. Cough makes us think that chee flow is not enough, at least in or within the lung ducts. It is important to open this flow so that the organ works sideways and downwards. After watching this flow, we will look at what needs to be done to open the flow. In the example above, cough is a lung-related symptom, a symptom, compared to acupuncture. This complaint could also be shortness of breath. Then the lungs come to mind again. This symptom may be palpitations. The organ associated with palpitations is the pericardium or heart. There may be hypertension. The organ involved in hypertension is the heart. The patient may have constant diarrhea. The organ involved in diarrhea is the spleen. The feet of the patient does not get hot at all. The organ that regulates heat is the kidneys. The patient is very irritable, quickly irritated, the organ responsible for this situation is the liver. These are just examples. Every organ has many basic complaints. We have collected these under approximately 100 complaint headings. These complaints can be found in many books under the title "Syndromes in Acupuncture".

2.11. Chi flow

Chi flow begins in the lungs and ends in the liver. In the closed meridian system, dirty dew coming from the liver is cleaned by coming back to the lungs and a new cycle begins. Qi flow is the flow of each Yin organ into a Yang organ that is its conjugate. Flow is seen in three groups of four organs. As we mentioned before, we called each group one cycle and created three-cycle acupuncture. We named the first cycle in the three cycles as the Lung cycle, the second cycle as the Heart, and the third cycle as the Liver cycle(6,7). Each cycle consists of four organs. It takes 8 hours for a cycle to occur. Three cycles are completed in 24 hours. At least four points are used in each treatment. These three floating loops are referred to as 4 needle treatments.

Figure 2 Chi flow in the channel

3. The first cycle is the lung cycle

The first cycle is the Lung cycle (Lung, Colon-Stomach, and Spleen). In this cycle, the Chi passes from the lung to the large intestines, from the large intestines to the stomach, from the stomach to the spleen. Yuan Chi from the lungs from the air, food from the Spleen and Kidneys combine to form the correct qi and this qi is collected in the Lungs. The correct qi in the lungs is sent to the whole body. Qi is sent from the lungs first to the large intestine, participating in the descent of the lungs. The peristaltic movements of the large intestines are more effective when enough dew is in the large intestine. Food pulp is advanced. Dew communicates with bacteria in the large intestine. In particular, it provides the necessary energy to nonpathogenic bacteria, with their regular work, the consistency of stool is formed in the large intestines, and the final adjustments of water absorption are made. The downward and lateral expansion of the lungs affects the diaphragm, helping the progressive movements of the large intestine of the diaphragm.

3.1. Pectoral Chi and Four Organs

The other two elements of the pectoral Qi cycle are the conjugate Yang organs of the two Yin organs. The Yang conjugate of the lungs is the Large Intestines and the Stomach of the Spleen. Both organs are in Yangming localization as localization. The large intestines are the Yang meridian of the hand and begin with the second finger. The stomach is the Yang meridian of the foot and it ends in the second toe of the foot. I think these two Yang organs are of equivalent frequency. Pectoral dew enables the lungs, heart, and all structures in the chest to work. Especially the lungs are very affected by the Pectoral Chi. For the pectoral chi to form sufficiently, it depends on the normal expansion of the lungs downward and sideways, and the ability of the spleen to work well, transforming the food from the stomach well and combining it with the Air qi. As food reaches the large intestine, they establish a relationship with the lungs and there is a qi circulation within these four organs. These organs consist of the Lungs, Spleen, Large Intestines, and Stomach. Pectoral qi is produced in this cycle. That's why we also call this cycle the "Pectoral chi cycle. This cycle is where the qi from the air meets the Chi taken from the food. The reason why it is called a cycle is that after the qi flows from the lungs to the spleen, it travels to all organs and then returns to the lungs through the liver. There are four organs in the pectoral qi cycle. Two of its organs are Yin and two are Yang organs. Yin organs are the Lung, the Taiyin meridian of the hand, and the spleen, the Taiyin organ of the foot. Pectoral Chi ensures the harmonious functioning of the diaphragm, bacteria, and large intestines, creates the proper consistency and shape of the stool, prevents diarrhea and constipation. From the large intestines, qi rises upward and enters the stomach. While the food that has been chewed in the stomach and turned into chyme passes into the small intestine, its chi is taken and sent to the spleen. The stomach plays an important role in sending nutrient qi to the spleen. This cycle is the first step of the three cycles. These two Yin organs are similar in localization. While the lung meridian ends at the thumb of the hand, the spleen meridian starts from the big toe of the foot and moves upwards from the inside of the foot. The two organs show a Tai course as localization. So they can be regarded as having the same energy frequency.

3.2. Treatment in the first cycle

After the complaint is received, the organ related to the complaint is determined and the cycle of this organ is determined. After the cycle is determined, the treatment is started with the Yuan points belonging to the organs that will ignite the Right Dew. During the treatment, at least 4 points are used. For the lung cycle, we select Lung Yuan point, Lu-9, Large Intestine point LI-4, St-42 as Stomach Yuan point, and Sp-3 as Spleen Yuan point. However, it would be more appropriate to choose St-44 instead of St-42 in the stomach. In addition to these points, well-known points of each channel can be added by looking at their additional complaints.

3.3. Use of points

Stimulation of points and length of stay After the points are pinned, the Yuan point of the organ related to the complaint is rapidly and intensely pinned bilaterally and the needles are turned and activated. After being pinned, the needles

remain for 25 minutes and then are removed. How many days is the cycle therapy done? Cycle therapy is done three times a day or every other day. Then the next cycle is passed.

3.4. A case related to the lung cycle

A dentist who has been suffering from headaches for two years. He has a severe headache, especially during tooth extraction, and stops the treatment. He takes painkillers and treats him where he stayed. He has not concluded with the treatments he has received so far. During the interrogation of the patient, he said that the pain appeared suddenly in the frontal region. Headaches involving the frontal region are related to the stomach canal and the large intestine canal. Since both channels are located in the lung loop, Yuan points in these channels were pinned. Stomach Yuan point: St-44 replaced instead of St-42 Spleen as Yuan point: Sp-3 Large Intestine as Yuan point: LI-4 As the lung Yuan point: Lu-9 point was applied. The patient's headache passed and He started to treat his patient.

3.5. The second case about the lung cycle

Taiyin cycle was applied to the patient who complained of abdominal swelling and irregularity in the urogenital due to after surgery of testicular Ca. Points LI-4, Lu-9, Sp-6, and St-44 were applied in the supine position. After lying down for 25 minutes, his needles were removed. The patient said that the swelling in the abdomen and the irregularity in the urogenital area had passed and he felt very comfortable.

3.6. The third case about the lung cycle

44-year-old female patient. She complained of diarrhea, vomiting, and nausea for two days. When he comes to us, he has mild diarrhea, vomiting and nausea continue. Diarrhea can be related to the spleen, large intestine. Nausea and vomiting were thought to be related to the stomach and were thought to be Taiyin syndrome, and Yuan points were selected from the Lung, Spleen, Stomach, and Large intestine meridians and they were injected and waited for 25 minutes. Using points, LI-4, Lu-9, Sp-6, and St-44. Immediately after the needles were withdrawn, the patient said that he felt well and had no complaints.

A patient under reflux treatment (N.C), a 46-year-old male patient

Reflü tedavisi gören bir hastamıza akciğer döngüsü tedavisi uyguladık. Hasta ilk geldiğinde sesi kısıktı, konuşması anlaşılıyordu, sırt üstü yatamıyordu Mide muhtevası özefagusu ve ses tellerini tahriş etmişti. Problem Mide kaynaklı, akciğerleri de etkileyen bir rahatsızlığa sahipti. Hasta artık iyileşme devresine girmişti. Tedaviyi akciğer döngüsü ile devam ettirmeye karar verildi. Lu-9, LI-4, Sp-6, St-44 uygulandı.

3.7. The second cycle-heart cycle

The heart takes dew from the spleen. Spleen energy has a dew that nourishes the muscles in particular. Dew from the spleen ensures proper, a sufficiently strong contraction of the heart muscles. Heart muscle irregularities do not appear with proper Spleen Dew. The spleen also adjusts the moisture and fluid amount of the blood in the heart, prevents heart blood from leaking between the tissue, prevents the formation of clots, sputum in the heart, and prevents blockages. Chi after the heart The small intestines pass and provides the necessary stimulation for the proper functioning of the small intestine. In particular, it provides water distribution, intestines temperature, intestines absorption, and passage to other organs. Qi passes from the small intestine to the bladder. It manages bladder retention, retention, and emptying of the urine. The bladder canal is the longest and most pointed channel in the body. It collects toxic substances in almost all areas of the body and ensures their excretion. Back These points of all other organs are on this channel. It is as if each point on the channel is related to both itself and other channels. The channel transfers its energy to the kidneys. The dew coming to the kidneys, together with the kidney dew, allows the kidney to perform the classical functions. Renal dew manages the bladder sphincters. All bone tissue is under the management of the kidneys. The kidneys of the mineral concentration play an important role. The kidneys also have a role in blood production.

3.8. The first case about the heart cycle

35-year-old male patient. Computer engineer. He spends close to eight hours in front of the computer every day. Primary complaint: The patient has persistent back pain. He cannot stand upright due to pain. Back pain increases when you stand upright. When the patient is asked to show the pain with his hand, the thoracic shows the Th-2-3-4 region. When the patient was placed on his back, there was sensitivity in that area. Because of these complaints, he had physical therapy and could not be treated despite using many painkillers. The area where the patient is disturbed mainly coincides with the Back Shu point of the heart organ. With these data, the patient was treated with a heart cycle consisting of the Small Intestines, Kidneys, and Bladder, based on the heart. H-7, SI-4, Kid-3, and UB-64 points were

selected for this. The patient was placed on his back. First, needle manipulation was performed by pinning the H-7 and SI-4 points from above. Then Kid-3 and UB-64 were made and the points were warned. After 25 minutes, the patient was removed. The patient stood more upright and the pain was completely gone.

3.9. The second patient of the cardiac cycle

The patient is a 19-year-old young girl. She complains of frequent urination, knee and back pain, extremely sensitive in her relationships. Her patient's complaints are about the bladder. The bladder, small intestine, heart, and kidneys are the organs of this cycle. Selected points Yuan points: H-7, Kid-3, UB-64, SI-4

After being injected, she was kept lying for 25 minutes. Supplemented with Kid-7 for bone pain. The patient exited the treatment in a very positive way.

3.10. The liver cycle

The third cycle is the liver cycle. In this cycle are Sanjiao, Pericardium, Gallbladder, and Liver organs. After receiving complaints about these organs, the Yuan points of the organs, Sj-4, P-7, GB-40, and Liv-3, are used. Although this cycle looks like the 3rd and last cycle, it is not. The important thing is that the patient's complaint belongs to the organs in this cycle.

3.11. A case related to the liver cycle

C.Y 42 years old female patient. He presented to the clinic with severe pain (with severity of 10/10) involving the right side of the patient's head. The patient is having menstruation and has headaches along with her periods. Pain It looks like a migraine-type pain. It was thought that there was a headache related to the gall bladder at the site of the disease. In this case, there may be a chi flow problem in the third cycle. It was thought that there was a problem in the liver-gallbladder-Pericardium-Sanjiao cycle. Points Li-3, GB-41, Sj, P-7 were selected and pinned. The GB-5 point, which is sensitive to pressing the right side of the head, and the right Taiyang point were added. After treatment, the patient's pain dropped to 5/10 in the first minute, then passed completely (0/10). Here, instead of Sj-4, which is the Yuan point of the Sanjiao canal, the Luo point Sj-5, and from the gallbladder ladder, GB-41 was used instead of the Yuan point GB-40.

3.12. The second case about the liver cycle

A 65-year-old female patient. Severe headache that has lasted for two days and is currently unresponsive to painkillers. Pain in the two temporal parts of the head, involving the eyes, a separate pain in the top of the head There are gallbladder and liver type pain depending on the involvement locations. There may be migraine pain. Pain intensity 10/10. According to the patient's statements, the patient is the patient of the liver cycle. Therefore, spots were selected from four organs of the liver cycle. The organs of this cycle are Pericardium, Sanjiao, liver, and gall bladder. Selected points: Instead of P-7, Sj-3 (Sj-4), GB-40, Liv-3 talked about some pain in the forehead after the patient was pricked. Therefore, GB-1 and GB-4 from the gallbladder meridian (sensitive to pressing). Ring-shaped pains occurred around the eyes during the treatment. The liv-2 point was chosen from the liver for these pains. In the first five minutes, his pains disappeared 90%. After the treatment, the pain is 100 percent gone.

4. Conclusion

Each new method is improved as it is used. This method also needs time for development. The simplicity of the method may lead to doubts that it is not effective enough. However, it has been used in the clinic for five years and as those who want to use it can see, it is effective enough. Preliminary studies have been made with its effectiveness and will be supported by a project that started before the pandemic but was carried out temporarily due to the pandemic.

One of the concerns about the method may be related to the point number. In three cycles, basically one point belonging to four organs is selected. However, this does not mean that the arrow point cannot be used. It can be added to the treatment at the points where the efficiency of the determined organs is well known. However, there is an obligation to use at least four points. As a general rule at least four points and four needles are used in the three-cycle acupuncture where the diagnosis is made from the symptoms. There are many important, well-known points about each organ. Therefore, the number of points can be increased.

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